

TASKS OF ANALYSIS AND TEACHING OF DISCOURSE IN MODERN SCIENCE

Kudaybergenova Sapura Polatbaevna

Karakalpak State University

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Review: In this article written about the role and place of language in the social life of an individual and society and discussing the problem of the formation of the conceptual apparatus of the theory of speech communication.

Key words: discourse, hypothesis, human speech, speech communication, social phenomenon.

The discussion, which began with the first works of B. Bernstein, where the so-called deficit hypothesis was formulated, generated a great literature and helped draw attention to the social determinants of speech, allowed linguists to more adequately recognize the role and place of language in the social life of an individual and society. Interest in speech communication, to the external components of the communicative act is supported by the reaction to the non-dialectical reduction of linguistics, which F. de Saussure carried out, limiting the subject of linguistics to the language system and excluding from the research practice human speech and speech communication.

A.A.Leontev, A.K.Markova analyzing the reasons for the emergence of pragmatic linguistics as a reaction to the exclusion of speech from the subject of linguistics, they write that this assumption (the practice of which is borrowed from the natural sciences, coming from the premise: nature is cunning, but not malicious) puts a sign of equality between natural objects and human social activity, which is essentially intentional and, therefore, active in relation to the process of generating speech. [1,116-117]

So, if we agree with the fact that in modern linguistics there is a tendency of an ever wider study of discourse realized within the framework of psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, linguistic pragmatics, then obviously there is a need to discuss the problems of the object, subject, methods of research of speech communication. [4, 38-41]

Below we have attempted to discuss these problems from the standpoint of the theory of discourse.

Discussion of the problems of discourse showed that research practice encounters the need to expand the object of research through non-verbal interaction of communicants. The expansion of the object and the restructuring of the subject matter naturally create a need for the formation of a conceptual apparatus that adequately reflects new fragments of the object of research and

provides theoretical constructions in the subject area of psycholinguistics, which takes into account not only internal psychophysiological, but also external, psychosocial factors of discourse.

The main objective of our work is to

- 1) show that the development of linguistics and within its development the development of psycholinguistics has led to the formation of prerequisites for studying the processes of speech generation and perception in a wide social context, in the structure of social interaction of communicants;
- 2) to analyze the nature of the connection of speech and non-speech components of social interaction between communicators, in whose structure the discourse is the only one unfolding;
- 3) to discuss the problem of the formation of the conceptual apparatus of the theory of speech communication (TRC), - that fragment of the theory of speech activity, the subject of which are the psychosocial factors of discourse.

When analyzing the prerequisites for the formation of the theory of discourse, it was shown that there are prerequisites external to the SEC and internal, which arose as a result of the need to resolve the contradictions of the process of research of verbal communication. Discourse theory is based on the conceptual basis of discourse, along with the advantages of the latter, and its weaknesses. Our main efforts are aimed at showing that the interaction of communicants, the need for servicing of which is the primary reason for the deployment of speech, is socially determined and is carried out in accordance with social norms, rules, standards adopted by a person in the process of socialization. Discourse, being a social phenomenon, is subject to the influence of the same norms, rules, standards as speech, naturally, in the discourse paradigmatic and syntagmatic rules are also realized.

On the basis of this idea of discourse as a social activity, other, internal reasons for the emergence of discourse were also considered - the problem of mutual understanding of communicants in the process of discourse and the problem of social regulation of the activities of communicants in the act of communication.

To build the subject of discourse, the relationship between activity, social interaction, communication, social (social) relations, relationships and speech communication was analyzed and shown. In turn, the written text can be presented as a transformed form of discourse, or rather acts of verbal communication, where speech arose, the written fixation of which became the subject of analysis.

To describe the external, social factors of discourse, the conceptual apparatus of discourse theory can be applied, interpreted in terms of the theory of roles, the structural-functional version of which is developed in the methodology of teaching foreign languages [5;45]

The main results of the work are in the theoretical formulation and discussion of a number of problems in the study of discourse and in the formulation of prerequisites for the construction of a theory of discourse, which significantly increases the explanatory power of the theory of discourse. This creates a certain theoretical basis for the deployment of empirical research, primarily in the field of speech influence, which plays a major role in the media system. In addition, the practical value of the work consists in forming ideas that can be used as the basis for teaching foreign languages, including Russian. The essence of this view is to understand the teaching of a foreign language as a process of forming the skills and abilities to communicate in a foreign language.

The increase in the relevance of discourse problems is also caused by the evolution of methods of appropriating culture in the process of socialization of society members: an increase in verbal methods of obtaining new knowledge, a sharp increase in the amount of knowledge that a member of society should acquire during socialization, reinforces the role of verbal methods of knowledge transfer, as this transfer occurs in form of discourse.

In modern society, the number of categories of workers is increasing, which should have the skills to build discourse, especially skills to hold a mass audience at a professional level.

However, naturally, the main customer for the study of the problems of discourse are public institutions that have an ideological impact on the mass audience.

The presence of such a social order led linguists to rethink their place in solving the social problems of society and turn to the study of discourse in the social coordinates of its functioning. Not least the attention of linguists to the social context of communication was drawn in connection with the problems of teaching native and foreign languages.

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